
BEST PRACTICES FOR QUALITY ENHANCEMENT IN S.S.G.M. LIBRARY

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7179846

Abstract:

Library is the heart of any educational institute and also most important part of our social life. Many peoples of our society, researcher and scholars are use library for reading and empowering their knowledge. In academic libraries researcher, students and scholars are most frequently users. By providing helpful and supportive facilities and implementation of best practices we can enhance our services. Because of the users requirement in higher education provide updated library services but in high school and junior level only books issue/return service apply. There is need to library user connect with library for forever. In that case libraries implement various best practices. Library of S.S.G.M.K. College also tried to provide best library services through best practices.

Keywords: Best practice, quality, S.S.G.M.K. library

Introduction:

In 21st century because of explosion of information and competition in each sector everybody required updated information. And everyone has wish to win first and that's why everyone to tries to update their knowledge by minute to minute. Also libraries are need to change. Libraries are provide SDI, CAS and Reference services, Reprography etc. To maintain and enhance quality of library services academic libraries need to run the various best practices for user. Like library automation with standard library software, news clipping service, internet service, carrier guidance service, book review competition, group discussion about newly published book, award to best user of the year etc. In this era academic libraries enhanced quality through various useful best practices.

Objective:

1. To important of best practices.
2. To enhancement of quality in academic libraries.
3. To attract library users through best practices.
4. To assurance quality through best practices.

Methodology:

Descriptive research methods have been used in the present research paper. For this, the best practices provided by the library were analyzed and how to improve library services through best practices. And we studied how to be constantly connected with our users. Studied innovative and useful best practices.

**Sushila Shankarrao Gadhave
Mahavidyalaya, Khandala:**

The Sushila Shankarrao Gadhave Mahavidyalaya is well known college in Khandala. S.S.G.M. Khandala college was established by the Khandala Vibhag Shikshan Samiti, in June 2007, for the purpose of providing quality education upto degree to the students in this area. Arts, Commerce and Science faculties in the college on permanent non-grant basis. Considering the need for technical education along with Science and Administrative education at present, the institute also started a vocational B.C.A. course on permanent non-grant basis from 2008.

Our college is affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur and is one of the best rural colleges of the university, in terms of academic, cultural. NSS. NCC and sport achievements. We have additional students of Yashwantrao Chavan Maharashtra Open University, Nashik.

The support services of the college include well-equipped science laboratories, Library, Playground, Tight security etc. The growth of the college is qualitative as well as quantitative. Our students have excelled in the sports, NSS activities at university and occasionally at state levels. Many of our students have occupied good positions in Administration, Teaching, Central and State Defense Services, Industry, Banking. The work of imparting quality education to the girls in this area has been done by college faculty.

About Quality:

The word use for various references by all mean. In library science, quality related services providing by library to users like students, researcher, faculties and readers also. To improve and assurance for consistently and the best

services in academic libraries use various type of best practices.

How to manage quality?

In this information era, academic librarian know to Who is our user? What are they want? And How to fulfill those requirements? "In a service organization like an academic library, customer satisfaction means, fulfilling expectations. Librarian must find out what readers want and what they did not want, so librarian concentrates upon providing it." [1]

Quality Enhancement:

Enhancement is a process of improvement. In relation to higher education quality, enhancement may refer to: (1) individual learners when it means improvement of the attributes, knowledge, ability, skills, and potential of learners; (2) the improvement in the quality of an institution or study programme. [2]

Best Practices:

"In the application of theory to real-life situations, procedures that, when properly, applied consistently yield superior results and are therefore used as reference points in evaluation of the effectiveness of alternative methods of accomplishing the same task. Best practices are identified by examining empirical evidence of success." [3]

About Library of S.S.G.M. Khandala:

In every academic institute library done most important and effective role. There are various requirement of users in this information explosion era. In this digital era the most critical problem against higher educational libraries how to connected users with us and provide advanced library services to users. And they stay continuous with library.

S.S.G.M. library have 11320 text and reference books and subscribe 27 journals on various subjects. Library use E-granthalaya software for automation. Our library has partially automated. To attract users S.S.G.M. library tries different ways. Library run innovative ideas and events celebration. Because of non-grant basis and due to lack of funds there are many limitations in our efforts. But various library services, quality based best practices are implemented by library department.

Best Practices of S.S.G.M. Library:

The implementation of certain techniques transforms the library into an effective learning center and motivates students to read in addition to textbooks, beyond just issuing and collecting books. And reference books are also provided for use in the reading hall.. The student is always attached to the library as the librarians love their job and work there.

Library Orientation and Use of NDLI:

To grow reading habits among the students library, arrange library orientation program from last two years. At the starts of academic year students have to know about rules and regulations of library and library services. Also know how to registration for National Digital Library of

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India and how to use NDLI? This library service has been useful for every student in college and first year student also. Use of maximum utilization of library resource and to keep connected with library, library orientation program will be enquire.

Displayed Library Charts:

Library displayed following charts in the library such as, library advisory committee, Rules and regulations of library, sections of library, and guides for every book racks. This will help to every user. Library give open access service to third year students and the students of competitive cell students. Motivational thoughts and quotes are displaying for inspiration of user.

Student of Competitive Cell:

For competitive cell students library provide extra transaction for competitive books. Displaying “Rojgar Varta” through newspaper cutting. Issue journals related to competitive exam.

New Arrivals and Book Exhibition:

Library organized book exhibition on specific occasion for collection in every academic year. And displayed newly arrive journals on various subjects. Readers are aware about library collection and resource.

Inter Loan Facility:

S.S.G.M. library connected with one of other college and one sarvajanic vachanalaya through MOU. We shared library resource, library app of other college. And also books of fiction, historical and many types of books.

Days Celebration:

Various days are celebrate from library department. On the occasion of Birth Anniversary of Dr. S. R. Ranganathan as National Librarian Day, Birth Anniversary of Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam as Vachan Prerana Din, National Book day on 23rd April. Library.

Other Best Practices:

Including above best practices library had provide other best practices like, Interact personally with students as needed, guide them, Book-bank facility, Readers club, Students Library Committee, Best Reader of the Year, Issued Reference books in Reading Hall against I-card etc.

Conclusion:

Users are the most important part of library because user's satisfaction is ultimate aim of library. In higher academic libraries we have to take care of user's expectations and try to provide maximum best service to them. First we need to understand their needs and then we can provide the activities and library services. It is our duty to motivate users and create awareness among the ease of use of various resources. Libraries are working as knowledge resource center, research center, information center and librarians are mediator, knowledge manager, and knowledge provider, information provider who provide valuable and updated information from the resource to its

beneficiaries or users. S.S.G.M. Library is giving very good library services to their users. We know that in this digital era, we have many limitations to provide ICT based library services. But always we try our best.

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